

SIMILARITIES IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES CULTURE

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Abstract: Globalization opened up the world and let people from different parts of the world enjoy what other cultures had to offer. People can pick up new languages and incorporate various cultures into their daily lives, resulting in the development of new ways of doing things. Around the world, different cultures have unique ways of doing things that may seem strange to outsiders. From a global viewpoint, some traditional cultures stand out because they are connected to past civilizations.

Keyword: Culture of different countries, tradition, education system, social evolution, socioeconomic evolution, social standards.

Introduction. Culture is defined as consisting arts, beliefs and institutions of a population that are passed down from generation to generation. Culture is called "the way of life for an entire society." As such, it consists of codes of manners, dress, language, religion, rituals, art. In its broadest definition, culture refers to the ideals that have been developed throughout human history and have become crystallized. In its earliest manifestations, culture emerges almost concurrently with the development of humans. Culture plays a unique and significant function in the social evolution of a society. Culture is the philosophical underpinning of society, yet it is simultaneously governed by how that society develops. Without a question, every culture has had a significant impact on how each nation has developed. Without the cultural silhouette exhibited or reflected in many forms, shapes, and angles, we can scarcely identify socioeconomic achievements. There are contemporary cultural items that have sprung from fresh realities, fresh occasions, and a clean environment of contemporary societies.

Studies employing various countries have produced conclusions that tend to focus on one issue and/or one region of the world in terms of cultural similarities, or the method to look for just communities across geographic contexts. Examples include issues like childhood socioeconomic position and late-adult mental health²⁹, mental health in European countries³⁰, age disparities in level of trust³¹, psychological issues, and fear of losing things³². Additionally, there are historical cultural artifacts that have been lost because they cannot function in today's stringent social tensions or are incompatible with it. Second, the process of development takes place within a framework of cultural exchange, as a result of both the preservation of the national culture and the assimilation of elitist values from other cultures. The exchanges between cultures in the developing phases of history is a reality that reflects the growing demands of nations and cultures. There are contemporary cultural items that have sprung from fresh realities, fresh occasions, and a clean environment of contemporary societies. Additionally, there are historical cultural artifacts that have been lost because they cannot function in today's stringent social tensions or are incompatible with it. Second, the process of development takes place within a framework of cultural exchange, as a result of both the preservation of the national culture and the assimilation of elitist values from other cultures.

Methods of analysis. During our research we found that all countries have their own culture and we can notice some kind of similarities and differences in their culture and their tradition. During our survey we noticed some countries tradition, culture, religion and their education system look like our country's culture and education system. Civilizations have always interacted, but this reality has changed as nations and cultures have become more demanding. Each country's progress reflects its cultural development in a proportionate way. In addition to being the foundation of a community, culture also strengthens a flexible force that is essential to the advancement of every country. Each country's culture has a variety of traits and facets that influence how each person looks.

Literature analysis. Similarities in different countries culture is described much more clearly and understandable in the book which is called "Ancient Political Thought" of the Antony Black book. The similarities and contrasts between two or

²⁹ Li T, Fung HH. Age differences in trust: An investigation Across 38 countries. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*. 2013;68(3):347-355.

³⁰ Yun RJ, Lanchman ME. Perceptions of aging in two cultures: Korean and American views on old age. *J Cross Cult Gerontol* 2006;21:55-70.

³¹ Allik J, McCrae RR. Toward a geography of personality traits: Patterns of profiles across 36 cultures. *J Cross Cult Psycho* 2004;35(1):13-28.

³² Young K. Gender and intergenerational co-residence in Egypt and Tunisia. *Popul Res Policy Rev* 2009;28(5):615-640.

more civilizations are taken into consideration while comparing them. As a result, each culture's relationship to other cultures has similarities and distinctions. Both the physical form and the abstract form of the similarity exist. Each country's culture has a variety of traits and facets that influence how each person looks. The similarities and contrasts between two or more civilizations are taken into consideration while comparing them. In the relationship between cultures, each culture has its similarity and difference. Customs, laws, dress, architectural style, social standards and traditions are all examples of cultural elements.

Italy, the home of pizza and sorbet, has always been a source of fascination for travelers. The nation welcomes an estimated 40 million tourists a year and is well-known for its Renaissance art. The pandemic caused a sharp decline in tourism in 2020, but efforts exist to revive the sector as more people receive vaccines to fend off the disease. The art, architecture, and food of the Italians are all highly developed cultures. Music and dance are frequently incorporated into Italian activities, whether they are family celebrations, semi-formal occasions, or neighborhood festivals.

French influence may be seen across history because they have been around for millennia. The French culture is known for its delectable cuisine, outstanding artwork, and picturesque settings. The French, who come in at number two among the most influential cultures, are renowned for their love of romance. In addition, the French made a name for themselves as the capital of fashion with the help of numerous well-known brands like Hermes, Louis Vuitton, Mugler, Chanel, etc. According to data from 2019, France welcomes up to 90 million visitors annually, demonstrating people's keen interest in the French way of life.

Spain, which is made up of several independent nations, comes in third on the list of various cultures. It ranks as the fourth most visited nation in the world and also has a rich creative history. The love of religious festivals and other cultural celebrations are a couple of examples of Spanish cultural customs. The entire neighborhood participates in Spanish parties, therefore they are enthusiastically enjoyed. During the festival of La Tomatina, tomato-throwing contests are popular worldwide. The almost 80 million visitors to Spain in 2019 are proof that tourists adore the country.

Chinese culture is one of the oldest in the world, which accounts for its extensive history and complex customs. Philosophy, manners, art, and moral principles have all been greatly influenced by this fascinating, ancient society. Chinese culture is distinct from other civilizations in that it has its own distinctive architectural, political, and religious systems. Examples of distinctive aspects of Chinese cultural tradition include a focus on strong family relationships and adhering to the hierarchy. Even in old age, children are supposed to be filial to their parents and make sure they have all they

require. There is no place for disrespect because the elderly are highly valued in Chinese society.

Results and analysis. People from various nationalities and socioeconomic backgrounds coexist in the United States. It is the hub of the film and entertainment industries and has a sizable population. Hollywood's impact is spread over the entire world because to the movies and music it creates that travel to even the most remote regions. People in the US hold a variety of cultural views, some of which include that everyone has individual rights and ought to be treated with respect regardless of their ethnicity or religion. With nearly 1.3 billion inhabitants, India is the nation with the second-highest population after China. India is a diversified nation with many beautiful natural landscapes to see as well as well-known historical sites like the Taj Mahal. In this nation, people of different religions live in harmony with one another, and there are an estimated 19 million tourists there each year. The first thing you observe in India, aside from the throngs of tourists, is how respectful and spiritual the locals are.

Another colorful and festive culture is that of the Mexicans. Mexican culture, which was influenced by the Aztecs and the Mayans, has roots in a fusion of Spanish and other native cultures. They place more stress on the value of family, participating in religious celebrations, and showing respect for elders. Mexicans like to listen to upbeat music, dress colorfully, and watch bullfights. In 2020, more than 23 million tourists traveled to Mexico to see this fascinating culture and its love of spicy food.

Conclusion. In the conclusion we can say the cultural activity does not spring up out of nothingness or emptiness. This activity must produce specific goods in both tangible and intangible forms that incorporate cultural values. Although this form or another form may not be as prominent in any society, these two forms will always coexist. There are no tangible cultural products that do not at least partially reflect immaterial ones, therefore the division into two categories has simply become relative. Making a sharp distinction between the cultural similarities and differences would be incorrect. The affirmation of cultural similarities does not imply a rejection of those distinctions. Globalization is now driving the fourth science's development and influencing a technological revolution, and the globe is entering this phase. Areas of social sciences where no culture can be excluded are faced with new opportunities and problems as a result of current trends toward globalization. The impact of globalization reduces the distance between countries physically, national boundaries are increasingly dissolving, and penetration among various sectors in countries is rising quickly, producing unmanageable results, among other things. Additionally, culture is facing both new chances and problems. Each country's cultures have never before had the chance to absorb cultural elites and values from other countries in such a quick and

varied fashion as they are doing now. However, culture has never before faced a greater risk of corrosion than it does now, including policies that certain nations have in place to suppress national cultural values. As a result, in the modern world, cultural similarities also have an equal outcome.

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